

STUDIES IN THE SANTALOL SERIES. PART IV. CHEMISTRY OF GUERBET'S SANTALIC ACID

By P. C. GUHA AND S. C. BHATTACHARYYA

Guerbet's santalic acid has been isolated from sandalwood oil and its properties thoroughly compared with those of α -santalol (prepared from α -santalol), from which it has been found to differ fundamentally. Both chemical and spectroscopic evidences indicate that the substance is probably a saturated tetracyclic sesquiterpene derivative, and hence different from both α - and β -santalol acids. The substance has now been named γ -santalol acid, only because of its occurrence in sandalwood oil.

Among the different constituents of sandalwood oil, the acidic substance first isolated by Guerbet (*Comp. rend.*, 1900, 130, 417) and named by him as santalic acid behaves rather peculiarly. From his results of analysis, he ascribed the formula $C_{18}H_{24}O_2$ to the substance and without advancing any other experimental evidences named the substance as above, meaning thereby that the substance was the corresponding carboxylic acid of santalol. At the time of Guerbet, very little information was known about the chemistry of α -santalol and anything obtained from sandalwood oil was expected in some way or other to be related with the former. From our investigations it has now been found that Guerbet's acid is a tetracyclic saturated compound having no structural relationship with α -santalol, and hence the name santalic acid suggested by Guerbet for this acid evidently on the assumption that it is derived from santalol, does not seem to be correct.

Later, Semmler (*Ber.*, 1907, 40, 1120, 1124) oxidised α -santalol to α -santalal and subsequently converted it into the corresponding carboxylic acid and correctly named it santalic acid, although the name α -santalol acid would have been more appropriate.

The properties of Semmler's α -santalol acid, prepared from santalol, do not seem to have been compared by him with those of Guerbet's natural santalic acid. Semmler's paper (*loc. cit.*) was published about seven years later than that of Guerbet (*loc. cit.*), but as Semmler named his substance also as santalic acid, it seems probable that he considered his acid to be identical with that of Guerbet, evidently because these two acids were known to possess nearly identical boiling points and percentage composition.

For a closer and detailed examination a small amount of Guerbet's acid has now been isolated from sandalwood oil, and its properties compared with those of Semmler's α -santalol acid. The data as given below are evidently not identical and rather anomalous.

	α -Santalol acid	Guerbet's acid
1. Mol. formula	$C_{18}H_{24}O_2$	$C_{18}H_{22}O_2$
2. Equivalent weight	234.326	235.3

	α -Santalal acid.	Guerbet's acid
3. Action of pot. permanganate	decolourises	decolourises
4. Unsaturation value (percamphoric acid)	one double bond	0.2 to 0.4 double bond
5. Spectroscopic evidence	—	mostly saturated
6. Boiling point	193°/9mm.	189°/9 mm.
7. n_D^{20} of the acid	1.5055	1.5057
8. B.p. of methyl ester	146°/9 mm.	141°/9 mm.
9. n_D^{20} of methyl ester	1.4910	1.4914
10. d_4^{20} of methyl ester	1.0021	1.02858

Although the equivalent weight, percentage composition, boiling points and particularly the refractive indices of the acids and their methyl esters are quite close, the densities and the unsaturation numbers of the methyl esters of the two acids are so wide apart that they can never be regarded as identical and there must be some fundamental difference between the two acids.

Critical examination of density.—It is a general rule that in any series of acids belonging to the same family, densities of the methyl esters decrease with the increasing molecular weights. Densities of the methyl esters of the different acids of the α -santalol series are given below :

Name of ester.	Density, d_4^{20}
1. Methyl teresantalate ($C_{11}H_{16}O_2$)	1.0320
2. Methyl nor-tricycloekasantalate ($C_{12}H_{18}O_2$)	1.0230
3. Methyl tricycloekasantalate ($C_{13}H_{20}O_2$)	1.0164
4. Methyl α -santalate ($C_{16}H_{24}O_2$)	1.0020

It is clear from the above Table that all the esters of the acids of the α -santalol series, including the methyl ester of α -santalal acid itself obey this generalisation; but the methyl ester of Guerbet's acid ($C_{16}H_{24}O_2$) possesses a density of 1.02858. Therefore, it cannot belong to the compounds of the α -series. Neither can it belong to the β -series, the members of which possess an additional double bond and consequently should possess even lower densities.

Spectroscopic Evidence and Unsaturation Number.—Determination of the unsaturation number of Guerbet's acid with percamphoric acid reveals that its unsaturation number lies between 0.2 to 0.4. This is a positive indication that it is a mixture of some saturated and unsaturated compounds. From the examination of the absorption spectra of the substance in the ultraviolet region, it is found to give a flat absorption curve (*vide curve*) like that of acetic acid. From these results the only reasonable conclusion can be that Guerbet's acid is a saturated compound mixed with some unsaturated compounds as impurities.

It will be shown in part V of this series that Guerbet's acid is accompanied in nature by a considerable amount of β -santalal acid, which has been isolated by the authors for the first time. The new substance possesses two double bonds and is a highly refractive liquid. The unsaturation number of 0.2 to 0.4 shown by Guerbet's acid may, therefore, be due to the presence of a small quantity of β -santalal acid, the complete separation of which from the former by the usual process of fractional distillation is extremely difficult.

Constitution.—It is possible that Guerbet's acid is probably formed in nature from α -santalol (perhaps formed from α -santalol by some natural process of oxidation) through some rearrangement and may possibly be a tetracyclic compound of the type shown below.

Thus according to the above postulation, it possesses a formula $C_{13}H_{22}O_2$ and is a tetracyclic isomer of α -santalol. That this type of rearrangement of α -santalol is not impossible is suggested from the exocyclic ethylenic structure of β -santalol advanced by Ruzicka and co-workers (*Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1935, 18, 355), as shown above.

The following facts are also in favour of the above tetracyclic saturated structure:

1. The compound possesses four fused rings and is saturated, consequently its methyl ester should possess a higher density than that of α -santalol and this is actually so.
2. The substance possesses a formula $C_{13}H_{22}O_2$ and is saturated. Therefore, taking the validity of the isoprene theory about terpenes, it should have a tetracyclic structure.
3. The acid does not form an anilide, the carboxyl group may therefore be tertiary.
4. Taking the tetracyclic structure to be correct the $(R_L)_D$ of the methyl ester becomes 70.01 which differs from the calculated value 69.33 (due allowance being made for the cyclobutane ring). The difference of 0.67 unit may be explained on the ground that the substance is always mixed with the isomeric β -santalol which contains two double bonds (part V) and consequently possesses a higher refractive index and a lower density—characteristic of the β -series.

An examination of Lorenz's formula $(R_L)_D = \frac{n^2 - 1}{n^2 + 2} \times \frac{M}{D}$ will indicate that if under

some circumstances n decreases and D increases, as will be the case, if Guerbet's acid is freed from β -santalol, there will be a sharp fall in the observed molecular refractivity. The difference between the calculated and observed values may then vanish.

As Guerbet's acid is different from α -santalol a new name γ -santalol is, therefore, suggested for it.

EXPERIMENTAL

Isolation of Guerbet's Acid.—Government-certified sandalwood oil (7 lbs.) was saponified by boiling for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour with sufficient amount of alcoholic potash (3%). Excess of alcohol was then distilled off and the residual oil poured into water contained in a big separating funnel, shaken thoroughly and then allowed to stand. The aqueous layer was separated and the oily layer was again extracted with water. The combined aqueous liquor was evaporated on the water-bath to a smaller bulk and shaken three times with sufficient amount of ether to remove any oily substance. The alkaline aqueous liquor was then acidified with cold dilute sulphuric acid and the oily acid layer which separated was taken in ether. The ethereal layer

after washing, was dried with anhydrous calcium chloride, filtered and fractionated under reduced pressure in a Claisen's flask to which a 18 cm. bulb-fractionating column had been fused. The distillate was collected in three fractions as follows:

Fraction A: b.p. up to 150°/1mm., mostly teresantalic acid

„ B: b.p. 150°-172°/1mm., mostly Guerbet's acid

„ C: b.p. 172°-188°/1mm., mostly β -santalic acid

Most of the Guerbet's acid was in fraction B. Fraction A on redistillation gave a higher boiling fraction which was added to the fraction B. The combined amount was then refractionated three times in a smaller flask with similar bulb arrangement and the fraction boiling at 166°/1 mm. was collected; yield 12.3 g.; b.p. 166°/1 mm.; 189°/9 mm.; n_D^{25} , 1.5021; n_D^{30} , 1.5055. The substance is thick syrupy in nature, insoluble in water and has a persisting smell. Silver salt, prepared in the usual way, is fairly stable towards light at the ordinary temperature. The substance is a weak acid and cannot be titrated with alkali. Equivalent weight was determined by ignition of the silver salt. (Found: Equiv., 235.30. C, 76.29; H, 9.72. $C_{13}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 76.88; H, 9.46 per cent. Equiv. 234.49).

Methyl ester was prepared from the silver salt and methyl iodide in absolute methyl alcoholic medium; b.p. 141°/9 mm.; n_D^{25} , 1.4892; n_D^{30} , 1.4915; d_4^{20} , 1.02858; d_4^{25} , 1.02483; $(R)_D$, 70.01. (Found: C, 77.20; H, 9.91. $C_{14}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 77.38; H, 9.77 per cent).

Santalal.—Chromic acid (4 g.) in glacial acetic acid (30 c.c.) was added to an ice-cold solution of pure α -santalol (10 g.) in glacial acetic acid (25 c.c.) and the solution stirred thoroughly for 15 minutes and then warmed on the water-bath for about 10 minutes. The oxidised mixture was poured into sufficient amount of water and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed thoroughly with water, dried with calcium chloride, filtered and distilled in vacuum. α -Santalal distilled at 153°/10 mm.; yield 4 g.

The *oxime*, prepared in the usual way, melted at 103°.

Nitrile.—The oxime (10 g.) was slowly refluxed for 2 hours with acetic anhydride (50 c.c.). Excess of the anhydride was decomposed with cold water. The nitrile was extracted with ether and purified by vacuum distillation, b.p. 163°/9 mm.; yield 5.6 g.

α -Santalalic acid.—The nitrile was dissolved in 15% alcoholic potash (200 c.c.) and refluxed on the water-bath for 12 hours. α -Santalalic acid, formed by the hydrolysis of the nitrile, was isolated in the usual way, b.p. 193°/9 mm.; n_D^{25} , 1.5055.

Methyl ester was prepared from the silver salt and methyl iodide, b.p. 147°/9 mm.; (corrected); n_D^{25} , 1.4910; d_4^{20} , 1.0021.

Absorption Spectra of Guerbet's Acid.—Methyl ester of Guerbet's acid was used in this investigation, purified carbon tetrachloride freed from chloroform being employed as the solvent. The absorption spectra were taken with the help of a Hilger Quartz Spectrograph in conjunction with a Specker photometer. Ilford's hyperpanchromatic plates (HP₂) were used for the photographs. Though the photographic density of the two spectra in juxta-position can be compared fairly accurately, still the probability of error in the value of extinction coefficient is certainly +5 to +10%. The molecular extinction coefficient was calculated from the equation

$$I = I_0 \times 10^{-E_m \cdot c \cdot d}$$

where I and I_0 are the intensities of transmitted and incident light; c is the concentration in gram mols./liter; d the thickness of the absorption cell in cm. The results have been plotted graphically.

Further work in this line to prepare some pure Guerbet's acid freed from the unsaturated impurities by ozonisation and the subsequent systematic examination of the pure compounds and its derivatives is in progress.

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORIES,
INDIAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE, BANGALORE.

Received June 2, 1944

STUDIES IN THE SANTALOL SERIES. PART V. ISOLATION OF β -SANTALIC ACID, A NEW CONSTITUENT OF SANDALWOOD OIL

By S. C. BHATTACHARYYA

A new monobasic acid of the molecular formula $C_{15}H_{22}O_2$ has been isolated from sandalwood oil. The substance contains two double bonds and consequently possesses a bicyclic structure and has been named β -santallic acid. The absorption spectra of the substance in the ultraviolet region have been investigated.

Among the different constituents of East Indian sandalwood oil which have so far been isolated (Simonsen, "Terpenes", Vol. II, p. 544) β -derivatives form a comparatively minor part. Except β -santalol and β -santalene all the other ingredients of the oil, so far isolated, are more or less connected with the tricyclic alcohol, α -santalol and its derivatives. About 4 g. of a new monobasic acidic substance of the molecular formula $C_{15}H_{22}O_2$ have now been isolated from the East Indian sandalwood oil. As revealed by oxidation with percamphoric acid, the substance contains two double bonds and consequently possesses a bicyclic ring structure. In all probability the substance appears to be the corresponding carboxylic acid of β -santalol and has therefore been named β -santallic acid. It is necessary to mention in this connection that the acid is an unknown substance and though β -santalol can be isolated in a pure state it has not been possible up till now, to prepare β -santallic acid from it. The preparation involves about 5 successive synthetic operations necessitating the use of a considerable amount of β -santalol which it is difficult to procure. A comparative study of this substance and its derivatives with those of α -santallic acid has been made. The results are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Name	Boiling point.	Difference in boiling point.	n_D^{20} .	Difference in n_D^{20} .
α -Santalol	155°/9 mm. }	38°	1.5037 }	0.0018
α -Santallic acid	193°/9 mm. }		1.5055 }	
Me- α -santalate	147°/9 mm. }	46°	1.4910 }	0.0145
β -Santalol	163°/9 mm. }	39°	1.5120 }	0.0016
New acid	202°/9 mm. }		1.5136 }	
Me-ester of new acid	157°/9 mm. }	45°	1.4989 }	0.0147

Thus, it is seen that the relationship existing between the boiling points and refractive indices of α -santalol, α -santallic acid and its methyl ester is quite analogous to that existing between β -santalol, the new acid and its methyl ester. It is also well known that the β -deri-